

MANAGEMENT CHALLENGES AND LESSONS LEARNT IN THE HEALTHCARE SYSTEM GENERATED BY THE PANDEMIC GLOBAL CRISIS

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Abstract

Purpose – We present the most important lessons learnt regarding managerial activity hospitals during the global healthcare crisis of 2020.

Methodology – We conducted extensive interviews with hospital managers or key persons with wide decisional involvement in health institutions in Romania who were directly involved in their role during the first four months of the pandemic crisis generated by COVID-19.

Findings - As we are facing a global healthcare crisis, the lessons we present from hospitals from Romania can be compared with lessons from other countries and the learnings should prepare the healthcare system for a better response in future.

Research limitations– We conducted the interviews in medical institutions from major cities in Romania, as the general procedure in the first stage of the pandemic consisted in transferring positive patients into the regional special equipped COVID-19 hospitals, also called first line hospitals. We mention the fact, that we also conducted interviews in hospitals that were not COVID-19 hospitals, but they had to operate as usual because of specific emergencies and both staff and patients were also exposed to the virus and could become source of spreading.

Practical implications – the conclusions we present should be taken into consideration by risk management specialists and all the persons acting in the managerial process of medical institutions.

Originality – the learnings and conclusions come from key persons directly involved in managing challenges on a scale that has never seen before in the medical system. By combining expertise from different fields like medicine, management, teaching, research, development and production, we organized the study by specific criteria in order to obtain valuable results. Some of the authors were also involved in the first line during the COVID-19 crisis.

Key words: Management challenges, Medical system, Global healthcare crisis

Introduction

November 2019, a new virus called COVID-19 was first identified in China. Two months later, the virus spread in the whole world and became the source of the largest global healthcare crisis ever faced by the medical staff world-wide. With implications beyond imagination, the COVID-19 pandemic affects almost all sectors of our life. Healthcare system, economy, finances, politics, education, even societies and technology are influenced by the pandemic. Social distancing becomes the new normality and citizens trust into authorities is tested. We encounter discipline vs social unrest, hope vs fear, economical breakdown vs massive support measures by different governments. Even concepts as democracy and human rights are highly disputed while the world fights on all fronts against the COVID-19 pandemic.

As no one would presume, the pandemic wave hit Romania unexpected. The medical healthcare system was heavy tested, especially in the first weeks of pandemic, when all the countries were fighting to get medical equipment and devices, protection masks from the largest producer in the world, China. As a direct consequence of globalization trends and permanent pressure on production costs in the past

decades, China with its impressive production capacity became indispensable to the world through its exports. We will only refer to the products needed by the medical system. As the largest producer was already highly affected by the virus, many other countries were trying to prepare and face the pandemic wave.

When taking into consideration the research and development and production processes of medical devices/equipment, we know, that this field is highly regulated which makes new production capacities very time consuming until to deliver the first products into the market. Especially in the European Union, which has a very protective legislative system, ensured by European Council Directives, the production facilities in medical field are very expensive and require huge amounts of time investments. What would be the new ratio between speed and compliance?

Governments all over the world took strict measures of social distancing in the hope of preventing the virus to spread. Economic, social and political consequences followed several weeks and after two months most of the countries gradually relaxed the restrictions. A second infection wave appeared in summer 2020, and at the moment it looks like most of the specialists involved in the medical system are preparing for a long run against the COVID-19 crisis.

Looking back to the first four months of this healthcare crisis we study the reactions of the medical system in Romania and look after learnings from key persons who were directly involved in the managerial process of first line hospitals and also specialized hospitals. Both were operating hospitals during the entire period, so they faced the major risk of infection and virus spreading.

Hypothesis

In order to present valuable results, we conducted a study organized in several sections. After extensive interdisciplinary collaboration we defined out hypotheses.

The first hypothesis refers to the effort of the hospital management to reduce the spreading of the virus. Because of the direct contact with infected patients, the proportion of infected medical staff was very high at global scale.

The second hypothesis consists in under or over evaluation of specific risks and measures. As the decision makers had few historical data and there were great differences between the spread rate and speed in different countries and very few valuable information regarding the virus and the reactions, we presume that many reactions and measures might have been wrong estimated.

Our third hypothesis looks forward to the future. As all the major crises in history brought also technological progress as consequence, we think that this major global healthcare crisis will bring significant progresses in many fields of our life. In this article, we will only consider the progress in the close related fields like medicine, healthcare management, production of medical devices, pharmaceuticals and training of medical specialists.

Methodology

Our hypotheses were confronted with the results of extensive interviews with hospital managers and key decision makers in the healthcare system. Although we developed a specific questionnaire, we also ensured enough space in order to not limit the valuable input from the first line. Our goal is to obtain valuable information in a format that can be compared and analyzed from experienced key persons. During our activity to validate or invalidate our theses, a more important aspect occurred, namely, to not undermine useful information that we might have overlook.

Results

Regarding the effort to reduce the spreading the most important measures to protect patients and medical staff rely on high quality adequate equipment, disinfection standard and protocols and epidemic selection of all patients by testing all patients. Another measure was the effort to reduce the number of patients, per day by filtering the emergencies. Also, the organization of the circuits in the hospitals and medical institutions helped significantly, but not all institutions had enough space to adapt to the crisis mode activity.

One of the greatest managerial challenge was to ensure the acquisition of medical supplies. We were facing a global crisis on masks, disinfectants, gloves, etc. the so-called basic equipment. Not only that prices were rising exponentially, but some of them could not be found on the market at all. A major factor which amplified the supplies crisis was the lack of local producers for such supplies. Since the whole world was depending on the Chinese exports, we all had major blockades in the supply chains.

In extreme cases, solutions were needed. One of them was the compensation of lack of UV lamps with long time ventilation of the rooms.

With consideration to the progress obtained in the last months in order to reduce the spreading of the virus in the hospitals and medical institutions, our interviews revealed several important aspects. First, we have a better, more effective selection protocols. The increased testing capacity helps all the hospitals and medical institutions react faster. Another essential progress we can find in the field of consumables, although still expensive, we can find them on the market. One of the reasons why we can find consumables on the market is the fact that with great speed all the European countries started producing medical consumables and the dependency from China was not strict anymore. Another great progress is estimated in the field of knowledge and communication. While in the beginning the unknown regarding this new virus was spreading fear and panic, now as we gather information and data regarding SARS-CoV2 we can treat it more adequate. As a general conclusion, all the key persons admit that the progress on knowledge is still very slow.

As most of the hospitals and medical institutions were not directly involved in the fight against COVID-19, in the attempt to minimize the number of patients and possible contamination, the government decided to close many medical institutions. Also, many sections in hospitals were closed or had the activity reduced, especially those who did not treat emergencies. Our next question reflects the consequences of this lock-down. In order to answer this question, we have to define two different categories. The public healthcare sector and the private one. For the first one, some specific measures were to reduce the activity if they were not COVID-19 hospitals. For the second one, the private sector, the lock-down brought heavy loss from the economic point of view.

The second part of this study presents the reactions in the medical healthcare system. As we were facing a global crisis, the fast reaction crisis style had to be adopted, as managerial style. One of the consequences of taking decisions very fast is the lack of calibration with the importance and impact of the decision. It is generally very common that fast decision making can easily bring to under or overreaction to many problems.

When asked what decisions from the last three months they would keep regarding the consumables, most of the answers we received were that they would implement the same measures regarding protection materials. The only difference is that they would like to buy materials directly from producers in order to obtain better delivery and commercial conditions. One other thing was the necessity to have enough quantities of supplies. The idea that we need to encourage local producers was very often heard.

In the field of human resources, our responders highly recommend that the staff should be organized in more shifts, the more and smaller shifts - the better, in order to protect some of the shifts in case of contamination. While most of them admit that most medical units had enough human resource, some complain that the personnel structure was under-dimensioned. Both categories admit that medical staff could have been relocated more efficient in case of supplementary bonuses. In case of private medical institutions that had to close because they were not directly involved in the fight against the COVID-19 pandemic, personnel costs are a heavy loss, and some private players might close the business after this period, other will recover very slow. For all units, the epidemiologic sorting before the beginning of the activity remains a mandatory measure. In the end, a general common solution appears to be more communication in the teams. Sometimes, because of lack of communication panic can appear. Large institutions should have communication trainings for all the responsible with communication.

Regarding the communication process during the first three months of the pandemic we can highlight some ideas. One of them is the importance of an aligned message between all layers, starting with, some say, WHO – World health Organization, Minister of Health and Medical Council. In the last period, due to lack of proper information but also because abundance of misinformation, we are facing a very dangerous involution of trust in authorities. A major role for this is played by the quality of communication. Another topic is the improvement of electronic information archive process.

Regarding the communication with patients we should include more telemedicine techniques. On the other hand, specific instructions for patients have to be very easy to understand and follow.

Although the mass-media had an abundance of governmental information campaign of public interest, some specialists consider that the media, also had a confusing role for the population regarding the debates on certain topics related to the impact of COVID-19 pandemic. Such impacts on human rights, political and economical environment were debated in press.

One last mention is related to the public health direction, DSP, who some specialists consider are heavily outnumbered and did not have the structure and capacity to inform both population and medical staff. In order to ensure an efficient information process, there could be at least two solutions. The first one is to enforce and grow the structures of DSP in order to manage the communication process with population but also with medical staff. Another solution would be to establish on national level a new institution with communication attributions for medical staff.

Based on the experience in the last three months, one of the appreciated administrative measures were the direct acquisition process which enables an easy and fast form to procure supplies and equipment.

Another suggestion is that every hospital with more than 100 beds should have its own epidemiologist.

In the third part of our study we present the most relevant aspects regarding the expectations to the future in the context of COVID-19 global healthcare crisis and the post-pandemic times. It is well-known that every major crisis led, during the history, to technological or social evolution. From this perspective, the year 2020 brought the greatest healthcare crisis of modern times.

When asked how the evolution of medical field in the next decade will look like, we received some very interesting point of views. While some think that the access to existing but expensive technology will become more accessible, other mentioned automatization with focus on efficiency. Almost everyone agrees that the progress will rely on technology. We have concluded with a general idea that the focus will slowly move from treatment to prevention, as prevention can be a more effective way to fight future possible pandemics.

The progress of medical equipment is expected to be accelerated because of the COVID-19 crisis. Until now we observed in the last three months governmental measures in order to rebuild some of our medical equipment producing industry. This field was sadly neglected and the integration in the European Union led this field almost to extinction. The reason is that the government did not negotiated fair conditions for the existing producers before and during the integration and in this field of heavy regulated industry producers of medical devices in UE need time and resources to adapt to the new European conditions. Nevertheless, we received answers that in the future the evolution of medical devices producers will evolve fast because of great competition on the international level and hopefully also on the national level.

The European Union is well-known for its extensive, highly documented procedures and standards. The key persons acting in managerial positions in hospitals and medical institutions expect that the certification process of medical devices will be accelerated because of the great need of such products on the market. In order to obtain this, they do not necessary expect lower standard, but at least less bureaucracy. In a similar way, the process of introducing new drugs on the market is expected to be easier, but only for the big pharmaceutical players.

One other interesting topic is related to the chance that online education in the field of medical specialists could present many opportunities. As the whole educational system was forced to switch in several days from traditional teaching to online environment and the system had measurable results without being forced to post-pond generations of students, it is obvious that online teaching will play role from now on and investments in specific technologies and techniques will for sure bring valuable results.

Discussion and conclusions

Confronting our results with the first hypothesis that refers to the effort of the hospital management to reduce the spreading of the virus we can conclude that the healthcare system consumed many efforts and capacities to react and avoid spreading the virus. From easy to understand instructions for all patients to well defined procedures for medical staff, with discipline and great effort, by organizing the

staff in different shifts in order to avoid contamination from one shift to another, this continuous effort shows its measurable result.

Our second hypothesis was that during the specific crisis-managerial style, it is often expected to under or over evaluate specific risks and take accordingly disproportionate measures. Although at the first view, our hypothesis would not stand, as most of the key persons that answered to our interview declared they would not change many things, we consider that there are specific fields like provisions with supplies and medical devices, human resource organization, communication inside the healthcare institutions and with the population were field where we had disproportionated reactions. Even the lock-down of all private stomatology institutions for several month is considered by some as an abusive decision.

Our third hypothesis referring to high expectations regarding the evolution in the field of medicine and medical technology after the global healthcare crisis of 2020 is confirmed. With more focus on prevention than treatment, relying on technology, with less bureaucracy and high competition, in the thrive to achieve national or local independence on producing medical essentials and with new opportunities in online medical education the evolution in the medical field is expected to be accelerated.

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